

Display Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name D:\Data\Gosia\2023\W. Sulik\23.10.20\MS-III-032_23.10.20_2.d
Method Tune_pos_Mid.m
Sample Name MS-III-032 Instrument impact HD 1819696.00156
Comment

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.3 Bar
Focus	Active	Set Capillary	4000 V	Set Dry Heater	200 °C
Scan Begin	400 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1500 m/z	Set Charging Voltage	2000 V	Set Divert Valve	Source
		Set Corona	0 nA	Set APCI Heater	0 °C

